

Metroon (Athens)

also known as “Sanctuary of the Mother of the Gods”

By Laura Gawlinski, Loyola University Chicago

Entry tags: Hellenistic Religions, Greece, Religious Group, Phrygia, Greek Cult, Greek Religions, Religious Place, Shrine, Archaeological monument, Mystery Religion

A shrine of the Mother of the Gods in Athens became connected to the archives of the city-state by the late 5th c. BCE. Based on evidence from written sources, it was incorporated alongside the records in the so-called “Old” Bouleuterion (Council House) after a new building for boule meetings was constructed. In the Hellenistic period (ca. 140 BCE), a new building definitively referred to as the Metroon was built over the remains of the Old Bouleuterion. The famous cult statue of the Mother by Agorakritos is known through many miniature copies.

Date Range: 409 BCE - 267 CE

Region: Metroon

Region tags: Greece, Attica

area where buildings housed the shrine of the Mother of the Gods in the Athenian Agora

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Other [specify]: none

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

Notes: Hellenistic Metroon

A single structure

– Yes

The structure has a definite shape

– Rectangular

↳ A group of structures:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

Notes: the shrine itself was probably in a single room within the building, but at least some sources suggest that the whole building was considered to be "the Metroon"

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Political

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Other [specify]: evidence that it was destroyed in Herulian invasion but not clear how

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– As the result of pillage

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

– Yes

Notes: Old Bouleuterion (incorporation of Metroon only known through written evidence)

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Square

↳ A group of structures:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

Notes: the shrine itself was probably in a single room (or courtyard) within the building, but the name suggest that the whole building was considered to be "the Metroon"

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Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

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↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

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↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: the new Metroon was built over it, but whether it was destroyed first or just dismantled is unclear

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: the Mother of the Gods

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Camp, J.McK. II, *The Athenian Agora Site Guide*. 5th edition (American School of Classical Studies at Athens 2010).

– Source 2: Munn, M.H. *The Mother of the Gods, Athens, and the Tyranny of Asia: A Study of Sovereignty in Ancient Religion* (University of California Press 2006).

– Source 3: Sickinger, J.P. *Public Records and Archives in Classical Athens* (University of North Carolina Press 1999).

– Source 1: Thompson, H.A. "Buildings on the West Side of the Agora," *Hesperia* 6 (1937): 1-226.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

↳ Type of feature

– Terracing

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://topostext.org/place/380238BMet>

– Source 1 Description: ToposText entry on Metroon

– Source 2 URL: <http://agora.ascsa.net/id/agora/monument/metroon?q=&t=monument&v=list&sort=&s=32>

– Source 2 Description: entry on Metroon (monument) in Agora Excavations database

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

↳ Type of excavation:

– Scientific

↳ Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1907-1908

↳ Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: excavations by the Greek Archaeological Society

Notes: footnote in Thompson cites Praktika, 1907, pp. 54ff.; 1908, p. 59; Judeich, Topographie2, pp. 331 ff., fig. 42

– Yes

↳ Type of excavation:

– Scientific

↳ Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1931, 1934-1935

↳ Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Excavations of the Athenian Agora (American School of Classical Studies at Athens)

– Yes

↳ Type of excavation:

– Scientific

↳ Years of excavation:

–Year range: 1895-96

↳ Name of excavation

–Official or descriptive name: excavations by German Archaeological Institute

Notes: footnote in Thompson cites Ath. Mitt., XXI, 1896, pp. 107 ff.; Ant. Denk., II, 1899-1901

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

–Other [specify]: the city of Athens

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Yes

↳ Specify

- Revelation occurred through divination

Notes: later myths about the introduction of the Mother may relate to an earlier establishment of her cult, perhaps in an archaic shrine in the Agora

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

- No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

- Yes

↳ Specify

- Expiation

Notes: later myths about the introduction of the Mother may relate to an earlier establishment of her cult, perhaps in an archaic shrine in the Agora

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

- Field doesn't know

Notes: some scholars argue that the Athenian politician Alkibiades had a role

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

- Expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

- No

Sources and Excavations

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Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Other [specify]: none

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

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Type of feature

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Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

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Notes: Hellenistic Metroon

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Notes: the shrine itself was probably in a single room within the building, but at least some sources suggest that the whole building was considered to be "the Metroon"

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Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: the Mother of the Gods

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

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Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

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↳ Specify

– Other [specify]: the city of Athens

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Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: some scholars argue that the Athenian politician Alkibiades had a role

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

↳ Cult statues:

– Yes

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Statues of humans:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: there is a mosaic in the building, but seems to date to a later use of the structure after it is no longer the Metroon

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: roof tiles aren't "decorative," but it seems that the stamps on the roof tiles that include "Mother of the Gods" are worth mentioning somewhere

↳ Other type of decoration:

– Field doesn't know

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: image of Mother of the Gods seated with animals

- ↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)
 - No
- ↳ Portrayals of afterlife
 - No
- ↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)
 - No
- ↳ Humans
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural narratives
 - No
- ↳ Human narratives
 - No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

- ↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

 - Square meters: 1140
 - Notes: Hellenistic Metroon 30.40m x 38.83m
- ↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:
 - Field doesn't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth
– No

↳ Sand
– No

↳ Clay
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Plaster
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Wood
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

Notes: conglomerate limestone for foundations, some local marbles for stairs and column bases

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

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Notes: roof tiles aren't "decorative," but it seems that the stamps on the roof tiles that include "Mother of the Gods" are worth mentioning somewhere

↳ Other type of decoration:

– Field doesn't know

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

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↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

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Notes: image of Mother of the Gods seated with animals

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– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– No

↳ Humans

– No

↳ Supernatural narratives

– No

↳ Human narratives

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Field doesn't know

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is divination present:

– No

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Field doesn't know

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Field doesn't know

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

– Field doesn't know

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Field doesn't know

Are formal burials present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Yes

↳ Is the cult statue visible:

– Yes

↳ Is the cult statue hidden:

– No

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

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↳ Is the cult statue visible:

– Yes

↳ Is the cult statue hidden:

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Field doesn't know

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Field doesn't know

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Field doesn't know

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

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Is maintenance of the place performed:

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Is it required:

– Field doesn't know

Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Field doesn't know

Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Field doesn't know

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– Field doesn't know

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– No

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– No

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):
– Yes

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):
– No

↳ Function for water management:
– No

↳ Part of the transportation network:
– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:
– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:
– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):
– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:
– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:
Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders
– Yes

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

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Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

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Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

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– Yes

Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Field doesn't know

Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– Field doesn't know

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

Public food distribution and/or storage:

– No

Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– Yes

Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– No

↳ Function for water management:

– No

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

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